

Reaction on Solid Support : Oxidation of 4'-O-Benzyl-2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-chalcone using Silica-bound Iron(III) Chloride

NAZNEEN PARVEEN^a, NIZAM U. KHAN^{a*} and M. K. LOGANI^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002

^bDepartment of Shared Resources, Temple University, School of Medicine, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, 19140, U.S.A.

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Silica-bound ferric chloride has been used for the selective oxidation of aryl ethers and some simple phenols^{1,2}. The oxidation of 2'-hydroxy-4,4',6'-trimethoxychalcone on silica-bound ferric chloride gave a dihydrobichalcone³ and that of benzylated phenols gave debenzylated products². Here we report⁴ the formation of rearranged and cyclised products on the reaction of 4'-O-benzyl-2'-hydroxy-4-methoxychalcone with silica-bound ferric chloride.

The reaction of 4'-O-benzyl-2'-hydroxy-4-methoxychalcone (**1**) with silica-bound ferric chloride yielded 3'-benzyl-4'-O-benzyl-2'-hydroxy-4-methoxychalcone (**2**), 3'-benzyl-2',4'-dihydroxy-4-methoxychalcone (**3**), 7-O-benzyl-4'-methoxyflavone (**4**) and debenzylated product 2',4'-dihydroxy-4-methoxychalcone (**5**). The formation of **2** indicates the intermolecular interaction of the substrate **1**. Coordination of oxygen of the benzyl aryl ether in **1** with silica-bound ether generates partial positive character on benzylic carbon, which brings about electrophilic substitution on **1** to give the products **2** and **5**. Compound **5** may also arise from debenzylation of **1**. The dihydroxychalcone

- 1: R¹ = R² = H, R³ = PhCH₂
2: R¹ = H, R² = R³ = PhCH₂
3: R¹ = R³ = H, R² = PhCH₂
5: R¹ = R² = R³ = H

(**3**) results from debenzylation of **2** or/and by electrophilic substitution of **5** with the benzylic carbonium ion generated from **1** or **2**. Cyclisation of **1** followed by oxidation gives **4**. Some minor unidentified products found are polymeric in nature. This indicates that the benzylated product is not converted to radical cation⁵ or phenoxy radicals⁶.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken on a Kofler hot microscope and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded in KBr and ¹H nmr spectra (300 MHz) in CDCl₃ or DMSO-d₆ with TMS as internal standard.

Chalcone (**1** (2 g, 5.6 mmol), dissolved in a minimum quantity of methylene chloride, was added to ferric chlo-

ride (1.8 g, 11.1 mmol) adsorbed on silica gel (60–150 mesh, 18 g). Nitrogen was bubbled in the reaction mixture for 0.5 h. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 6 h. The crude product (1.5 g) was extracted with methylene chloride and water, and then with ethyl acetate. Tlc examination of both extracts gave the same result. Both the extracts were mixed and purified by column chromatography. Elution of the column with benzene gave a solid which was further purified by preparative layer chromatography (SiO₂, benzene-EtOAc, 30 : 1) as yellow crystals : **2** (45 mg, 5%), m.p. 150° (CHCl₃ : MeOH), R_f 0.78 (benzene-EtOAc, 30 : 1), brown in uv-light and black on absorption of I₂; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 1 610, 1 550, 1 525, 1 445, 1 380, 1 320, 1 275, 1 230, 1 170, 1 110, 1 045, 990, 840 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃; 300 MHz) 3.86 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.09 (2H, s, CH₂Ph), 5.16 (2H, s, OCH₂Ph), 6.54 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5'), 6.94 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-3,5), 7.19–7.36 (10H, m, 2×C₆H₅), 7.46 (1H, d, J 15.5 Hz, H-α), 7.60 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-2, 6), 7.80 (d, J 9 Hz, H-6'), 7.85 (1H, d, J 15.5 Hz, H-β); m/z (rel. int.) 450.2 (5.3), 359.2 (6.6), 298.1 (2), 283.1 (2), 240.1 (2), 225.0 (13), 211.1 (2), 197.0 (2.6), 180.1 (4), 161.0 (6.6), 141.1 (4), 134.1 (9.3), 121.1 (8), 103 (4), 91 (100) and 65 (13.3). Its structure was assigned as 2'-hydroxy-3'-benzyl-4'-O-benzyl-4-methoxychalcone (**2**). Further elution of the column with benzene gave the starting material (**1**) which was crystallised from ethyl acetate (325 mg).

Elution of the column with benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) gave a mixture of four compounds, which were further purified by preparative tlc (SiO₂, benzene-EtOAc, 30 : 1) as compounds **3**–**5** and a compound of polymeric nature.

Compound **3** (86 mg, 8%), m.p. 200°, was crystallised from ethyl acetate, R_f 0.3 (benzene-EtOAc, 30 : 1); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400, 1 630, 1 550, 1 515, 1 445, 1 380, 1 300, 1 250, 1 175, 1 110, 1 040, 830, 800 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃; 300 MHz) 3.86 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.09 (2H, s, CH₂Ph), 6.40 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-5'), 6.94 (2H, d, J 8.73 Hz, H-3',5'), 7.25–7.32 (5H, m, Ph), 7.47 (1H, d, J 15.1 Hz, H-α), 7.6 (2H, d, J, 8.7 Hz, H-2,6), 7.87 (1H, d, J 15.1 Hz, H-β); m/z (rel. int.) 360.2 (36), 226.1 (6.6), 197.1 (22.6), 161 (9.3), 141.1(16), 134.1(100), 121.1 (60), 115.1 (20), 103.1 (16), 91(10), 77(17.3), 65.0 (24) and 51.1 (7.2). It was assigned